

ISic3202

I.Sicily inscription 3202

Language

Latin

Type

uncertain

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: 074061

1. [---]LI[---]

2. [--- pra]ep(osito) D[---]

3. [---? nume]ro eq[uitum ---?]

4. [--- leg(ionis) secunda]e Trai[anae ---?]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175830

EDR 074061

EDCS 13700402

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

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